

DFT investigation of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole adsorption on model oxidized copper surfaces and relationship with corrosion inhibition

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Abstract

2-mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT) is known as an efficient corrosion inhibitor for copper. In the present work, we performed quantum chemical DFT calculations of the interaction of MBT on Cu(111) surfaces covered by an ultrathin Cu₂O(111) film, in order to bring atomic scale insight on the corrosion inhibition properties of MBT on oxidized copper surfaces. Thione and thiolate forms of MBT are found to interact strongly with the oxidized surfaces. The formation of a monolayer at full coverage is favored over single molecular adsorption at low coverage with the molecules adopting a perpendicular orientation. Thione binds strongly via covalent bonding between the exocyclic sulfur atom and the under coordinated Cu site, and additional H-bonding between the NH group and surface oxygen atoms (NH...O H-bond). Thiolate binds more strongly via a second covalent bond between the N atom and saturated Cu site. Bonding interaction is confirmed by the electronic structure analysis and charge transfer. The adsorption process leads to the reconstruction of the topmost oxide surface. The calculations suggest that both forms of MBT may substitute H₂O and OH at the Cu₂O film surface, and thus may form a protective layer on oxidized copper surfaces in aqueous environment.

Keywords: 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, Copper, Oxide, Corrosion, Organic inhibitor, DFT

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 Corrosion of metals and alloys is an ubiquitous phenomenon with huge
3 economic impact, which affects many industrial sectors. Its prevention is thus
4 a crucial issue. One of the solutions to mitigate corrosion is the use of organic
5 corrosion inhibitors [1, 2, 3, 4], that are considered as promising candidates
6 to replace chromate-based coatings [5, 6, 7]. Various organic compounds
7 containing nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur heteroatoms, polar functional groups,
8 and conjugated double bonds are used to prevent the corrosion of copper
9 [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

10 Among these organic molecules, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT) has been
11 shown to improve the corrosion resistance of copper in various conditions. In-
12 deed, MBT exhibits different active sites and may have different types of in-
13 teraction with the surface (H-bonding, electrostatic, covalent bonding). Still,
14 the question of the detailed interaction and monolayer formation of MBT in
15 its various forms (thiol, thione, anionic) on copper surfaces in metallic or
16 oxidized or passivated states, remains opened.

17 Several experimental works showed that MBT exhibits corrosion inhibi-
18 tion efficiency on copper. Chadwick and Hashemi [18] studied the corro-
19 sion inhibition of copper by MBT and MBI (2-mercaptobenzoimidazole) in
20 different experimental conditions (pH, immersion time and presence of Cl
21 and copper ions) using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and X-ray
22 induced Auger spectroscopy (X-AES). They found that the formation of a
23 Cu-MBT film is possible under all conditions and that the organic film thick-
24 ness depends on the pH of the treatment solution, which reflects the stability
25 and thickness of the Cu_2O passivating surface oxide. In the Cu_2O stability
26 domain ($\text{pH} > 4$), the thickness of organic films cannot exceed the mono-
27 layer without copper ions in the solution, whereas, in the Cu_2O instability
28 domain ($\text{pH} < 3$), the thickness of the organic film may be increased to any
29 desired value. Ohsawa and Suetaka [19] used various spectroscopy techniques
30 in order to clarify the mechanism of corrosion inhibition of Cu by MBT and
31 showed the formation of a surface film that acts as barrier isolating the metal
32 from the corrosive media. The mechanism would consist of the surface reac-
33 tion of cuprous ions with adsorbed MBT and not of a complex precipitated
34 from bulk solution and involving the ionized thiol form and copper ions in
35 ethanol solution [20]. Because corrosion processes are highly sensitive to pH,

36 Ramírez-Cano et al. [21] imaged in situ the pH distributions produced in
37 the surrounding electrolyte by the interaction of MBT with copper by using
38 scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) in potentiometric mode. They
39 concluded that the presence of an adsorbed MBT film on Cu shifts the pH
40 towards more alkaline values in a small volume of NaCl solution.

41 Some studies also investigated the adsorption sites and film formation in
42 different experimental conditions. Finšgar and Merl [22] showed using elec-
43 trochemical techniques that in chloride media MBT acts as mixed-type (i.e.
44 anodic and cathodic) inhibitor on copper. The surface layer thickness was
45 estimated to be 1.5 ± 0.5 nm and the adsorption of the thione form (MBTH)
46 via the N and exocyclic S atoms to Cu was concluded from XPS measure-
47 ments. Kazansky et al. [23] determined similar adsorption mechanism of
48 MBT in neutral phosphate media. However, Woods et al. [24] investigated
49 by Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) the interaction of MBT
50 with copper, silver and gold surfaces. They found that MBT chemisorp-
51 tion on all three metals involves bonding between the exocyclic S and metal
52 atoms. They concluded using XPS, that the surface layer is of monolayer
53 thickness. In contrast, Shahrabi et al. [25] reported that the adsorption of
54 inhibitors (MBT, MBI and MBO) on copper in sulphuric acid solution is
55 physical via electrostatic interaction and that no covalent bonding between
56 inhibitor molecule and metal surface is established.

57 The synergistic effect of MBT with other species has been established. He
58 et al. [26] investigated the corrosion inhibition of MBT with and without the
59 presence of halide ions on copper in sulfuric acid solution. They concluded
60 that the growth kinetics of the Cu-MBT film depends on the concentra-
61 tion of ions and that I^- promotes the synergistic formation of the protective
62 film. Bao et al. [27] used MBT to develop antibacterial coatings, aiming
63 to solve microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC) problems. MBT doped
64 chitosan/11-alkanethiolate acid composite coating was found to improve cop-
65 per protection (anticorrosion and antibacterial) in NaCl solution and in the
66 presence of sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB). Moreover, the MBT molecule
67 inhibited both anodic and cathodic reactions [20, 21, 25, 27].

68 The surface state of copper has an impact on MBT adsorption. Chadwick
69 and Hashemi [18] demonstrated the influence of the oxidation state on MBT
70 adsorption. Kazansky et al. [23] suggested that a thin Cu_2O layer is required
71 for the formation of the MBT layer, which thickness would depend on the
72 immersion time in neutral phosphate media. Recently, Chen and Erbe. [28]
73 reported using in situ infrared and Raman spectroscopy that in reducing con-

74 ditions in alkaline electrolyte, MBT forms a monolayer on the oxide free Cu
75 surface and prevents oxide formation. The inhibiting effect of a pre-adsorbed
76 monolayer of MBT on oxide formation is also found from studies of adsorption
77 from the gas phase on surfaces prepared in well-controlled conditions under
78 ultra low pressure [29, 30]. Thus, it appears that the oxidation state of the
79 Cu surface (metallic or covered by an oxide layer) is a determining factor in
80 the interaction of MBT with copper.

81 MBT also interacts with other metal and metallic alloy surfaces and
82 can be used for the protection against corrosion of aluminum and its al-
83 loys [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37], steel [38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43], brass [44, 45] and
84 nanocomposite [46]. Others studies investigated the corrosion and lubrica-
85 tion properties of MBT on bronze [47] and self-healing coatings properties on
86 magnesium and its alloys [48, 49]. The adsorption geometries of MBT mono-
87 layers on zinc [50], silver [24, 51, 50] and gold [24, 52, 53, 54] surfaces and gold
88 nanoparticles (AuNPs) [55] were also investigated by various experimental
89 techniques.

90 Thus, although corrosion inhibition is well established, the adsorption
91 mechanisms of MBT, including the role of the surface oxide, are still subject
92 to discussion and theoretical calculations are missing to clarify the MBT-
93 copper interaction. Quantum calculations approach can help us to under-
94 stand how inhibitors build up protective barriers against corrosion by inves-
95 tigating the interaction mechanisms on metallic and oxidized surfaces at the
96 atomic and sub-atomic scales.

97 Very few quantum chemical studies addressed the MBT molecule and its
98 adsorption. Theoretical calculations of the molecular properties showed that
99 the molecule can exist in different forms in solution [42] and suggested that
100 the thione form is a better inhibitor for steel than the thiol form. Cen et
101 al. [38] proposed that MBT adsorbs via N and exocyclic S atoms on carbon
102 steel (Fe). The combined first-principles and experimental study of Zhang
103 et al. [56] showed that MBT is more able to protect Cu(220) and not able
104 to protect Cu(200) and Cu(111) surfaces in the metallic state at low Cl
105 concentration. MBT was found to adsorb via physical bonding on Cu(200)
106 and Cu(111), while it chemically bonds via two sulfur atoms on Cu(220).
107 The highest chemical activation of the (220) face would drive the better
108 anti-corrosive ability than on the (200) and (111) faces. Vernack et al. [57]
109 studied MBT (thiol, thione, thiolate) adsorption on Cu(111) surfaces in the
110 metallic state. They found that the most stable configuration is that of a
111 monolayer of the thiolate form in a perpendicular orientation and adopting

112 a (3×3) superstructure, the molecules being bonded to the Cu atoms via
113 the exocyclic S atoms on Cu(111) surface. Bonding to Cu atoms via the S
114 atoms was confirmed by an experimental study of the adsorption of MBT
115 from the gas phase on oxide-free Cu(111) surfaces controlled at the atomic
116 scale [29, 30]. The thermal stability of MBT on clean and pre-oxidized copper
117 surfaces was studied experimentally at different temperatures [29, 30]. The
118 authors showed no desorption of MBT for temperature lower than 100°C ,
119 and decomposition and partial desorption for temperature above 100°C

120 From the examination of literature data, it thus appears that the adsorp-
121 tion of organic inhibitors on metal and alloy surfaces and the formation of
122 protecting layers is well established. The affinity of MBT with the metallic
123 Cu surface has been clearly demonstrated by experimental [29, 30, 28] and
124 theoretical [57] data. However, to the best of our knowledge, no theoretical
125 studies of MBT adsorption on oxidized copper surfaces has been performed
126 to complement the experimental knowledge. Indeed, depending on pH and
127 potential, the Cu surface will be oxidized or reduced [58].

128 Here we report a Density Functional Theory (DFT) study of the adsorp-
129 tion of MBT on an oxidized Cu surface. Modeling a metal surface covered
130 by a ultrathin oxide layer is a challenging task. Most often, the strategy is
131 either to use a metal surface covered by an oxygen or water overlayer, or
132 the termination of a bulk oxide. On Cu(111), Gharachorlou et al. [59] mod-
133 eled one monolayer of Cu_2O on the Cu surface and Park et al. [60] modeled
134 only a mildly oxidized (p4:O/Cu(111)) copper surface, while other groups
135 [61, 62, 63] modeled oxidized Cu surfaces by considering the termination of
136 a Cu_2O bulk structure.

137 Here we use a much more realistic model for the Cu surface passivated
138 by a surface oxide (Cu(111)|| Cu_2O (111)) derived from experimental studies.
139 In order to better understand the role of the oxide layer, two thicknesses
140 were considered. On these models, the MBT molecule was adsorbed and the
141 molecular coverage, molecular conformer and energies of adsorption were sys-
142 tematically investigated. The adsorption of MBT is compared to water and
143 OH adsorption in order to investigate in which conditions MBT is adsorbed
144 at the solid/liquid interface with the passivated surface.

145 2. Computational details

146 All calculations were performed in the framework of DFT with the peri-
147 odic plane-wave basis set code VASP (Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package)[64,

148 65, 66, 67]. All results reported have been obtained with projector-augmented-
149 wave potentials using a 450 eV plane-wave cut-off [68, 69]. The Gener-
150 alized Gradient Approximation (GGA) of Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE)
151 functional was used for the exchange–correlation term [70, 71]. We used a
152 Methfessel–Paxton smearing [72]. Because of the large unit cell size used in
153 calculations, the Brillouin-zone sampling was restricted to the Γ -point [73].
154 Van der Waals contributions were considered in the local van der Waals den-
155 sity functional scheme proposed by Dion et al [74] and Klimeš et al [75, 76, 77]
156 and calculations were carried out using OptB86b-vdw level [76]. Atomic po-
157 sitions were relaxed with the conjugate gradient (CG) algorithm until forces
158 on each moving atom were less than $0.02 \text{ eV}\text{\AA}^{-1}$.

159 In the unit cell, the substrate is represented by four layers of copper
160 metal having the (111) orientation and covered by a (111)-oriented Cu_2O
161 ultrathin oxide film with thickness of 5.89 or 11.07 \AA . The description (choice
162 of functional, construction, optimisation, energetic and electronic properties
163 and reactivity with water and OH groups) of the model was detailed in
164 our previous work [78, 79]. In the literature, the adsorption of molecules,
165 including MBT, on substrate surfaces is routinely modelled with different
166 GGA functionals [57, 61, 62, 80, 81]. Only a summary is given below. The
167 MBT molecules were adsorbed on top of the oxide layer. The vacuum region
168 was set at more than 18 \AA to minimize the interactions in the z direction
169 between periodic images of the system.

170 *2.1. Passivated surface model*

171 Fig.1 shows the constructed model of the passivated surface as derived
172 from experimental data [82, 83, 84, 85, 86]. The model elaborated for
173 the oxidized $\text{Cu}(111)||\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ surface consists of the $\text{Cu}(111)$ metal sub-
174 strate covered by the stoichiometric $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ oxide film in parallel epitaxy:
175 $\text{Cu}(111)[110]||\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)[110]$. Because of the perfect fit between the oxide
176 and metal substrate lattices over a coincidence length of 17.87 \AA [83, 86], we
177 use the lateral dimensions of the supercell of 17.81 \AA in both x and y di-
178 rections, which corresponds to (7×7) and (6×6) supercells for $\text{Cu}(111)$ and
179 $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$, respectively.

180 The two studied thicknesses of the oxide structure, 5.89 \AA and 11.07 \AA ,
181 correspond to two and four $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ layers, respectively. The oxide layers
182 are kept free to move. The two bottom layers of the $\text{Cu}(111)$ metal are
183 fixed and two interface layers are kept free to move, aiming to optimize the
184 interface interaction with the oxide film.

Figure 1: Snapshots of Cu(111) covered by two or four Cu₂O(111) oxide layers with different oxide surface states (top view and side view). Before relaxation (a) and after relaxation in the (b) dry, (c) hydrated and (d) hydroxylated surface states.

185 For the adsorption of the organic molecule, we considered three surface
 186 states of the oxide layer as shown in Fig.1. In the dry surface state, the
 187 bare Cu₂O(111) surface exhibits two distinct copper sites: coordinatively
 188 saturated (*csa*) and coordinatively unsaturated (*cus*) Cu atoms, labeled as
 189 Cu_{*csa*} and Cu_{*cus*}, respectively. It contains also two distinct oxygen sites:
 190 saturated and unsaturated oxygen ions, labeled (*O_{dn}*) and (*O_{up}*), respectively,
 191 where the subscripts indicate that they are located below (*dn*) and above
 192 (*up*) the surface Cu layer, as illustrated in Fig.2. The high symmetry of
 193 the unsaturated copper atoms is broken by lateral relaxation toward one or
 194 two adjacent saturated copper ions, which can affect the molecule adsorption
 195 topologies.

196 We also investigated the adsorption of the molecules on the hydrated

Figure 2: Surface sites of Cu₂O(111). Cu_{cus} and Cu_{csa} correspond to unsaturated and saturated copper surface sites, respectively. O_{up} and O_{dw} correspond to unsaturated and saturated oxygen surface sites, respectively.

197 and hydroxylated surfaces. Indeed, in contact with an aqueous solution,
198 the surface can be covered by a layer of water molecules or by OH groups
199 [78]. On the hydrated surface, the water molecules bind on top of Cu_{cus}
200 sites via the oxygen atom and form H-bonds with adjacent O_{up} oxygen. The
201 adsorption energy is -1.10 eV/mol at saturation of the Cu_{cus} sites. On the
202 hydroxylated surface, two types of OH bonding, named μ_1 -OH and μ_2 -OH
203 groups are found. μ_1 -OH corresponds to OH adsorbed on top of Cu_{cus} atom,
204 whereas μ_2 -OH corresponds to OH adsorbed in bridge mode between Cu_{cus}
205 and adjacent Cu_{csa} copper atoms. The adsorption energy at saturation is
206 -3.72 eV/mol.

207 The supercell described here allows us to study MBT adsorption at low
208 (0.37 mol/nm²) and high coverage (3.27 mol/nm²). The low coverage corre-
209 sponds to one molecule per supercell and the high coverage to nine molecules
210 per supercell, i.e. one molecule is adsorbed on each unsaturated copper site.

211 2.2. Molecules

212 The MBT molecule was modeled in thione (MBTH) and radical thiolate
213 (MBT[•]) forms (Fig.3). The properties of the MBT molecule have been de-
214 scribed in the literature. In the crystal structure, the molecules form centro-
215 symmetric hydrogen bonded dimers [87, 88]. In dilute solution, MBT ex-
216 ists as thione monomer and cyclic dimer [89, 90]. Experimental [89, 47]

217 and theoretical [57, 90] works revealed that the thione form is more stable
218 than the thiol form, and thus the thiol form was not modeled in the present
219 work. The isolated molecules were optimized in a box with dimensions of
220 $20\text{\AA} \times 20\text{\AA} \times 20\text{\AA}$ in x, y, and z directions, using the same computational con-
221 ditions described above. For the radical MBT° form, spin polarization was
222 implemented to get the energy minimum.

Figure 3: Isolated MBT molecule under the thione (MBTH) and thiolate (MBT°) forms modeled in this work

223 2.3. Energetics

224 The adsorption energy of the thione form (MBTH) was calculated as:

$$E_{ads} = [E(\text{slab}/\text{MBTH}) - E(\text{slab}) - nE(\text{MBTH})]/n \quad (1)$$

225 where $E(\text{slab}/\text{MBTH})$ is the total energy of the system with MBTH ad-
226 sorbed on the slab surface. $E(\text{slab})$ and $E(\text{MBTH})$ are the energies of the
227 bare, relaxed $\text{Cu}(111)|\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ slab and of the free MBTH molecule opti-
228 mized in vacuum, respectively. n is the number of molecules on the surface.

229
230 The adsorption energy for the radical thiolate form (MBT°) was calcu-
231 lated as:

$$E_{ads} = [E(\text{slab}/\text{MBT}^\circ) - E(\text{slab}) - nE(\text{MBT}^\circ)]/n \quad (2)$$

232 where $E(\text{slab}/\text{MBT}^\circ)$ is the total energy of the system with MBT° ad-
233 sorbed on the slab surface. $E(\text{MBT}^\circ)$ is the energy of the free radical MBT°
234 optimized in vacuum and n is the number of radical adsorbates on the surface.

235

236 In order to compare the stability of the formation of dense layer at full
237 coverage with the adsorption at low coverage, we normalized the adsorption
238 energy per unit area as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{norm} = E_{ads} \times \theta \quad (3)$$

239 where E_{ads} is the adsorption energy per molecule and $\theta = \frac{n}{A}$ is the cov-
240 erage, defined as the number of adsorbed molecules (n) per area (A) of the
241 slab.

242 We evaluated the interaction of MBTH and MBT° with the hydrated
243 surface considering a substitution reaction, where MBT replaces H_2O on the
244 surface covered initially by water molecules and water molecules are released
245 after adsorption. The reaction is:

246 where H_2O_{ads} stands for adsorbed H_2O molecules and MBT_{ads} for ad-
247 sorbed MBT molecules (MBTH or MBT° form). The corresponding substi-
248 tution energy is calculated as:

$$\Delta E_{subst} = [E(slab/MBT) + nE(H_2O) - E(slab/H_2O) - nE(MBT)]/n \quad (5)$$

249 where $E(slab/MBT)$ is the total energy of the system with MBT (MBTH
250 or MBT°) adsorbed on the slab surface. $E(H_2O)$ is the energy of a water
251 molecule calculated in the vacuum. $E(slab/H_2O)$ and $E(MBT)$ are the en-
252 ergies of the optimized structures with the water molecules adsorbed on the
253 surface and the free MBTH or MBT° form optimized in vacuum, respectively.
254 n is the number of adsorbed (or released) molecules.

255

256 We also evaluated the interaction of the thione form (MBTH) with the hy-
257 droxylated surface. The following condensation reaction (replacement of an
258 OH group by the MBT° form and release of water molecule) was considered:

259 where OH_{ads} stands for a surface OH group and MBT_{ads} for an adsorbed
260 molecule under thiolate form after reaction. The corresponding condensation
261 energy is calculated as:

$$\Delta E_{cond.} = [E(slab/MBT^\circ) + nE(H_2O) - E(slab/OH) - nE(MBTH)]/n \quad (7)$$

262 where $E(\text{slab}/\text{MBT}^\circ)$ is the total energy of the system with MBT thi-
263 olate (MBT°) adsorbed on the oxide surface. $E(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ is the energy of a
264 water molecule calculated in the vacuum. $E(\text{slab}/\text{OH})$ and $E(\text{MBTH})$ are
265 the energies of the optimized hydroxylated slab surface and the free MBTH
266 thione form optimized in vacuum, respectively. n is the number of adsorbed
267 MBT molecules.

268 2.4. Electronic and charge analysis

269 We plotted the charge density difference expressed as follows:

$$\Delta\rho(r) = \rho(r)_{\text{slab/mol}} - (\rho(r)_{\text{slab}} + \rho(r)_{\text{mol}}) \quad (8)$$

270 where $\rho(r)_{\text{slab/mol}}$ is the charge density distribution on the adsorbed sys-
271 tem, $\rho(r)_{\text{slab}}$ and $\rho(r)_{\text{mol}}$ are the charge density distributions on the isolated
272 slab and the molecule for the geometry after adsorption, respectively.

273 The net charge variation was determined on each atom by:

$$\Delta Q(x) = Q_{\text{ads}}(x) - Q_{\text{vac}}(x) \quad (9)$$

274 where $Q_{\text{ads}}(x)$ and $Q_{\text{vac}}(x)$ are the net charges on each atom (Bader pop-
275 ulation analysis) [91] of the adsorbed and free molecule, respectively.

276 3. Results and discussion

277 3.1. Adsorption topologies and energetics

278 The main question to answer is whether the molecules may adsorb on the
279 oxidized surface and what are the most favored configurations obtained for
280 a full MBT layer. The molecules were adsorbed on the dry, hydrated and
281 hydroxylated surfaces.

282 The molecule-surface distance was set at around 4 Å, and after geometry
283 optimization, the molecule was found adsorbed on the surface which indicates
284 bond formation, as will be described below. A wide range of configurations
285 were tested, considering: i) the different possible adsorption sites present
286 on the topmost surface plane; ii) the different reactive sites of the molecule,
287 which are the exo (S_{exo}) and endo (S_{endo}) cyclic sulfur, and the nitrogen
288 atoms; iii) the orientation of the molecule with respect to the surface plane.
289 We considered perpendicular, tilted and parallel orientations. Among all ad-
290 sorption configurations investigated in this study, we discuss here the most
291 relevant ones. An intuitive nomenclature is used to describe the adsorbed

292 configurations. For example (S_{exo} - Cu_{cus} , NH - O_{up}) means that MBTH forms
 293 two bonds, one between the exocyclic sulfur (S_{exo}) atom and the unsaturated
 294 copper (Cu_{cus}) atom, the other one between the NH function and the oxygen
 295 atom located "up" (O_{up}) in the topmost oxide plane.

296

297 The energetics of MBTH and MBT° adsorption at low and high coverages
 298 is compiled in Table 1. As we did not find any difference for the adsorption
 299 mode of MBT on the models with two or four oxide layers, we discuss here
 300 in details only the case where Cu(111) is covered by two $Cu_2O(111)$ oxide
 301 layers. The adsorption energy as function of the number of oxide layers is
 302 reported in each Figure.

	Low coverage (0.37 mol/nm ²)			Full coverage (3.27 mol/nm ²)			$\Delta E_{subst.}$ (eV/mol)	$\Delta E_{cond.}$ (eV/mol)
	Fig.	E_{ads} (eV/mol)	ε_{norm} (J/m ²)	Fig.	E_{ads} (eV/mol)	ε_{norm} (J/m ²)		
MBTH	Fig.4	-3.40	-0.20	Fig.5(a)	-2.71	-1.42	-1.61	-
MBT°	Fig.6	-4.60	-0.27	Fig.7(b)	-2.96	-1.55	-1.87	-1.35
				Fig.7(d)	-2.94	-1.54	-1.84	-1.33
				Fig.8(a)	-3.11	-1.63	-2.01	-1.50

Table 1: Energetics of MBT adsorption at low and full coverage on Cu(111) covered by two layers of $Cu_2O(111)$. blue

E_{ads} is the adsorption energy on the dry surface, calculated with Equations 1 and 2, ε_{norm} is the adsorption energy normalized per unit area, calculated with Equation 3. $\Delta E_{subst.}$ is the energy of substitution on the hydrated surface (Equation 5) and $\Delta E_{cond.}$ the energy of condensation on the hydroxylated surface (Equation 7).

303 *3.1.1. Adsorption of thione form (MBTH) at low (0.37 mol/nm²) and full*
 304 *coverage (3.27 mol/nm²)*

305 Fig.4 shows the most stable configuration obtained at low coverage. The
 306 molecule is tilted toward the surface (meaning rings nearly parallel to the
 307 surface). The adsorption energy is -3.40 eV/mol and ε_{norm} is -0.20 J/m².
 308 MBTH binds via the S_{exo} atom to a Cu_{cus} atom with a bond length of 2.17
 309 Å. A $NH...O$ hydrogen bond with an O_{up} atom is also formed and the dis-
 310 tance $NH...O$ is 1.61 Å. In addition, two carbon atoms of the aromatic ring
 311 are involved in the interaction mechanism. These carbon atoms (correspond-
 312 ing to C_6 and C_9 in Fig.3) are bonded to adjacent Cu_{cus} atoms with C-Cu

Figure 4: Snapshot and adsorption energy of the most stable adsorbed configuration of thione form (MBTH) at low coverage. E_{ads} value in brackets corresponds to the adsorption energy of MBTH adsorbed on Cu(111) covered by four Cu₂O(111) oxide layers.

313 bond lengths of 2.16 Å and 2.19 Å.

314

315 At high coverage, the molecules stand perpendicular to the surface in the
316 most stable configuration (Fig.5(a)). The S_{exo} atom and the NH group are
317 directed toward the surface. MBTH forms a covalent bond between the S_{exo}
318 and a Cu_{cus} atoms with a bond length of 2.15 Å and an H-bond between
319 the NH group and an unsaturated oxygen (O_{up}) surface atom (1.38 and 1.70
320 Å for NH...O). The adsorption direction from Cu_{cus} to O_{up} on the surface

321 is favored over Cu_{cus} to O_{dn} by the formation of the H-bond (Fig.5 (a) and
322 (b)). The adsorption energy is -2.71 eV/mol and less favorable than at low
323 coverage. However, the normalization of the adsorption energy to a unit area,
324 $\varepsilon_{norm} = -1.42 \text{ J/m}^2$, shows that the formation of a full monolayer is much
325 favored compared to the adsorption at low coverage. The adsorption of the
326 molecule via both the exo and endocyclic sulfur atoms is less stable as shown
327 in Fig.5 (c) and (d).

328 3.1.2. Adsorption of thiolate form (MBT°) at low (0.37 mol/nm^2) and full 329 coverage (3.27 mol/nm^2)

330 The situation for the thiolate is different since the molecule cannot form
331 a H-bond with a surface oxygen. However, the nitrogen atom can interact
332 directly with surface copper atoms. In addition, the reactivity of the molecule
333 may be different in the radical form as compared to the neutral form.

334 The most stable adsorption configuration of MBT° at low coverage is a
335 tilted orientation toward the surface (meaning rings nearly parallel to the
336 surface), like for MBTH form (Fig.6(a)). Indeed, MBT° binds via the exo-
337 cyclic sulfur to an unsaturated copper atom with a bond length of 2.18 Å.
338 Two carbon atoms (C_6 and C_9 in Figure 3(b)) are also involved in the inter-
339 action mechanism with bond lengths $\text{C}\dots\text{Cu}_{cus}$ of 2.11 Å and 2.14 Å. MBT°
340 also forms a covalent bond via the nitrogen atom with a saturated copper
341 atom with a bond length of 1.91 Å. The adsorption energy is -4.60 eV/mol
342 ($\varepsilon_{norm} = -0.27 \text{ J/m}^2$), which is more stable by 1.20 eV/mol than for MBTH.
343 However, the competitive adsorption of both forms under the following mech-
344 anisms ($\text{MBTH} + * \longrightarrow \text{MBT}_{ads} + \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2$ or $\text{MBTH} + * \longrightarrow \text{MBT}_{ads} + \text{H}_{ads}$)
345 showed that MBTH is more favored by 0.35 and 0.23 eV/mol, respectively.
346 The results reveal that the competitive adsorption of MBT° is favored only
347 in the presence of both species (thione and thiolate) in the same solution.

348
349 The surface atoms involved in the interaction undergo reconstruction (
350 Fig.6(c)) as compared to the bare surface before adsorption (Fig.6(b)). De-
351 hydrogenation of the molecule (MBT°) makes the nitrogen more reactive
352 towards the substrate surface. The saturated copper atom is pulled out by
353 breaking of the $\text{O}_{dn}\dots\text{Cu}_{csa}$ bond due to the formation of the $\text{N}\dots\text{Cu}_{csa}$ bond,
354 and the $\text{O}_{dn}\dots\text{Cu}_{csa}$ distance increases from 1.86 to 2.69 Å. Another change
355 in the surface structure concerns the neighboring unsaturated copper atom,
356 which moves and binds with the unsaturated oxygen (O_{up}) atom, the dis-
357 tance decreasing from 3.10 to 1.89 Å.

Figure 5: Snapshots and adsorption energies of different adsorption configurations of MBTH form at full coverage and illustration of the adsorption mode. Top, adsorption through exocyclic sulfur atom and NH functional group and orientation relative to the surface sites, (a): (S_{exo} - Cu_{cus} bond; $NH-O_{up}$ bond) and (b): (S_{exo} - Cu_{cus} bond; $NH-O_{dn}$ orientation). Bottom, adsorption through exo and endocyclic sulfur atoms and orientation relative to the surface sites, (c): (S_{exo} - Cu_{cus} bond; S_{endo} - O_{up} orientation) and (d): (S_{exo} - Cu_{cus} bond; S_{endo} - O_{dn} orientation). E_{ads} values in brackets correspond to the adsorption energy of MBTH adsorbed on Cu(111) covered by four $Cu_2O(111)$ oxide layers.

Figure 6: Snapshots and adsorption energy of the most stable adsorption configuration of thiolate form (MBT°) at low coverage (a) and surface structure of Cu₂O(111) film after adsorption (b) and before adsorption (bare surface) (c). E_{ads} value in brackets corresponds to the adsorption energy of MBT° adsorbed on Cu(111) covered by four Cu₂O(111) oxide layers.

358

359 Different adsorption configurations studied at full coverage are shown in
 360 Fig.7 and Fig.8. In order to compare with the interaction of MBTH (Fig.5),
 361 we addressed similar adsorption configurations of MBT° bonded to Cu and
 362 O surface atoms as shown in Fig.7. The most stable configuration of MBT°
 363 is in Fig.8(a). The unstable (Fig.7(c) and Fig.8(b)) and less stable (Fig.7(a))
 364 configurations are not further discussed below.

365 At full coverage, MBT°, like MBTH, adsorbs in a perpendicular orienta-
 366 tion. Interestingly, the adsorption via S_{exo} and N atoms or via S_{exo} and S_{endo}
 367 atoms, noted (b) and (d) in Fig.7, respectively, are iso-energetic. The ad-
 368 sorption energy is -2.95 ± 0.01 eV/mol ($\epsilon_{norm} = -1.55$ J/m²) and more stable
 369 by 0.25 eV/mol than for MBTH. This competitive adsorption is valid only
 370 in the presence of both species (thione and thiolate) in the same medium,
 371 as explained for low coverage case. MBT° binds only via S_{exo} atom to an
 372 unsaturated copper atom, with a bond length of 2.12 Å. The distance from
 373 the S_{endo} and N atoms to the O_{dn} atom is 3.15 ± 0.03 and 4.48 ± 0.03 Å,
 374 respectively. These MBT° adsorbed configurations are oriented from Cu_{cus} to

Figure 7: Snapshots and adsorption energies of different adsorption configurations of MBT° form at full coverage and illustration of different adsorption modes. Top, adsorption through exocyclic sulfur and nitrogen atoms and orientation relative to the surface sites, (a): ($S_{\text{exo}}-\text{Cu}_{\text{cus}}$ bond; N- O_{up} orientation), (b): ($S_{\text{exo}}-\text{Cu}_{\text{cus}}$ bond; N- O_{dn} orientation). Bottom, adsorption through exo and endocyclic sulfur atoms and orientation relative to the surface sites, (c): ($S_{\text{exo}}-\text{Cu}_{\text{cus}}$ bond; $S_{\text{endo}}-\text{O}_{\text{up}}$ orientation), (d): ($S_{\text{exo}}-\text{Cu}_{\text{cus}}$ bond; $S_{\text{endo}}-\text{O}_{\text{dn}}$ orientation).

375 O_{dn} direction, whereas it is from Cu_{cus} to O_{up} direction for the most stable
 376 configuration of MBTH.

377 The most stable adsorbed configuration of MBT° , noted (a) in Fig.8, has
 378 an adsorption energy of -3.11 eV/mol ($\epsilon_{\text{norm}} = -1.63$ J/m²). The normaliza-
 379 tion to the unit area shows again that the full monolayer adsorption is favored
 380 compared to the low coverage adsorption. MBT° binds via S_{exo} atom to an
 381 unsaturated copper atom, with a bond length of 2.12 Å. In addition, MBT°
 382 forms a covalent bond via its nitrogen atom with a saturated copper surface,
 383 with a bond length of 1.98 ± 0.04 Å.

384

Figure 8: Snapshots and adsorption energy of different adsorption configurations of MBT° at full coverage and illustration of different adsorption modes. (a) adsorption through exocyclic sulfur and nitrogen atoms and orientation relative to the surface sites (S_{exo}-Cu_{cus} bond; N-Cu_{csa} bond). (b) adsorption through exo and endocyclic sulfur atoms and orientation relative to the surface sites (S_{exo}-Cu_{cus} bond; S_{endo}-Cu_{csa} bond).

385 We recall that on bare Cu₂O(111) surface the high-symmetry of the Cu_{cus}
 386 atom is broken due to lateral relaxation towards adjacent Cu_{csa} ions. At full
 387 coverage, the adsorption of the molecule under MBTH and MBT° forms on
 388 top of the Cu_{cus} atoms lifts the reconstruction of the bare surface (Fig.9)
 389 and the bulk high-symmetry is recovered. Thus both forms of molecule stabilize
 390 the Cu_{cus} sites. However, for the most stable adsorbed configuration
 391 of MBT° shown in Fig.8(a), the Cu_{csa} atoms are also involved in the interaction
 392 mechanism. The nitrogen atom pulls out the Cu_{csa} atom with elongation
 393 of the O-Cu_{csa} distance (average of $\Delta d = 0.12 \text{ \AA}$), indicating a quasi-bond
 394 breaking (Cu_{csa}...O_{dn} or Cu_{csa}...O_{up}) compensated by bond-making between
 395 Cu and N atoms (Cu_{csa}...N).

396
 397 Comparison of the adsorption energies (E_{ads}) calculated by Equations 1
 398 and 2, and substitution energy (E_{subs}) calculated by Equation 5, from the
 399 mechanism defined by Equation 4, shows that the formation of an MBTH or
 400 MBT° adsorbed monolayer at full coverage is much more exothermic than

Figure 9: Surface structure after adsorption of MBT (top) compared to bare surface structure (bottom). Top left corresponds to all adsorption configurations of MBTH and MBT° with one covalent bond of the molecule to the Cu_{cus} atom (circled). Top right corresponds to the configuration in Fig.8(a) with two covalent bonds of the molecule to the Cu_{cus} and Cu_{csa} atoms (circled).

401 that of a molecular water layer (Table 1). Indeed, we calculated substitution
402 energies of -1.61 and -2.01 eV/mol for the most stable monolayer configura-
403 tion of MBTH (Fig.5 (a)) and MBT° (Fig.8 (a)), respectively. This means
404 that in both forms the MBT molecule is able to substitute a water monolayer
405 on the hydrated copper oxide surface. However, the substitution mechanism
406 of hydroxyl groups, $\text{OH}_{ads} + \text{MBT} \rightarrow \text{MBT}_{ads} + \text{OH}$, is unfavored for
407 both the MBTH and MBT° forms. For these reasons, we considered the
408 condensation reaction of MBT° (Equation 6) with the corresponding energy
409 calculated by Equation 7. The results show that this condensation reaction
410 is very exothermic with calculated energies of -1.34 ± 0.01 eV/mol for (b) and
411 (d) configurations in Fig.7 and -1.50 eV/mol for (a) configuration in Fig.8.
412 These calculations suggest that the MBTH form would be able to replace
413 surface OH groups by forming adsorbed MBT° and releasing water but that
414 the MBT° form would not be able to directly substitute surface OH groups.

415

416 We can conclude that whatever the surface state of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ oxide

417 film on Cu(111) (anhydrous, hydrated or hydroxylated) the adsorption of
418 MBT (under thione and thiolate forms) is favored and MBT can form dense
419 and ordered monolayer with a density of 3.27 mol/nm², which could explain
420 the experimental results on the formation of the protective film on copper
421 under different conditions [18, 19]. However, the adsorption mode depends on
422 the thione or thiolate form of the MBT molecule and the copper surface state
423 (covered or not by oxide). The thione form (MBTH) is adsorbed via covalent
424 bonding of the S_{exo} atom on Cu(111)||Cu₂O(111) surfaces, which corresponds
425 to the bonding reported from experimental measurement on oxidized copper
426 by Woods et al. [24]. The thiolate form (MBT^o) is adsorbed via covalent
427 bonding of both the N and S_{exo} atoms on Cu(111)||Cu₂O(111) surfaces, in
428 agreement with the bonding reported from XPS measurements by Kazansky
429 et al. [23] and Finšgar and Merl [22]. On the metallic surface not covered by
430 any oxide, the adsorption via covalent bonding of both exo and endocyclic
431 S atoms was calculated to take place on metallic copper [57] and observed
432 experimentally by XPS [29, 30]. This type of bonding was also observed on
433 metallic gold by STM measurements [52].

434 3.2. Electronic structure analysis

435 Electronic structure analysis provides more details about the molecule-
436 surface interaction. This can be done using the density of states (DOS),
437 the projected density of states (PDOS), the integral local density of states
438 (ILDOS) and the visualization of the molecular orbitals. It can be also done
439 by analysis of the charge density variation ($\Delta\rho(r)$) and charge transfer (Δ
440 Q) as defined in Equations 8 and 9, respectively. A combined analysis of
441 all these data brings relevant information useful to understand the nature
442 of the reactive sites involved in the binding process, the amount of charge
443 transferred from/to the surface, and the reactivity of the molecules towards
444 substrate surfaces.

445

446 3.2.1. Isolated species (before adsorption)

447 The total density of state (DOS) analysis of the isolated thione (MBTH)
448 form is shown in Fig.10 (middle). There are several S, N, C and H atoms
449 in the molecule, and hence, we projected the density of states (PDOS) for
450 every type of atom, as shown in Fig.10 (bottom). The molecular orbitals of
451 the isolated molecules and the integral range are shown in Fig.10 (top). We
452 represented the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO-1 and HOMO)

453 and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals LUMO and LUMO+1, with iso-
454 surface of $+0.004 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$.

455

456 The DOS shows that the HOMO is located near the Fermi level of the
457 slab at about -0.40 eV and that the LUMO is located 2.70 eV above the
458 Fermi level. These HOMO and LUMO alignments relative to the Fermi level
459 suggests that MBTH can easily exchange electrons with the surface and be-
460 haves more as an electron donor than electron acceptor during the adsorption
461 process. The PDOS reveals that the occupied states near the Fermi level are
462 dominated by the contribution of the exocyclic sulfur orbitals (green line).
463 Thus, the exocyclic sulfur atom is the most reactive species and it is the most
464 likely site for the interaction with the surface copper atoms. We also observe
465 a small contribution of nitrogen and endocyclic sulfur atoms to the DOS,
466 which is visible at HOMO and HOMO-1 levels. The LUMO and LUMO+1
467 levels show the contribution of all atomic orbitals of the molecule in the
468 unoccupied states. Analysis for the isolated thiolate anion shows similar
469 characteristics.

470

471 *3.2.2. Adsorbed molecules at full coverage*

472 Fig.11 depicts the ILDOS (top) at different integral range, the PDOS on
473 the molecule (middle) and for every atom (bottom) for MBTH adsorbed at
474 full coverage. It corresponds to the most stable adsorbed configurations in
475 Fig.5(a).

476

477 The comparison of the ILDOS and DOS projected on the molecules be-
478 fore and after adsorption, reveals drastic changes in the electronic structure
479 of the molecule, indicating a strong molecule-surface interaction. We observe
480 peak shifting, peak broadening, and the appearance of new peaks in the den-
481 sity of states after adsorption. Two peaks located below the Fermi energy
482 at -1.50 eV and -3.60 eV are dominated by the DOS of the exocyclic sulfur
483 atom. The ILDOS reveals that the peak at -1.50 eV is similar to the sulfur
484 contribution at HOMO before adsorption and that the peak at lower energy
485 (-3.60 eV) is associated to the sulfur-copper binding. It can be concluded
486 that the interaction via the exocyclic sulfur with the copper atom is very
487 strong and it is the only atom involved in the covalent binding of MBTH on
488 $\text{Cu}(111)||\text{Cu}_2\text{O}(111)$ surface.

489

Figure 10: Electronic structure analysis of the isolated MBTH form of MBT: integral local density of states (ILDOS, top), density of states (DOS, middle) and projected density of states (PDOS, bottom).

Figure 11: Electronic properties of adsorbed MBTH at full coverage: visualisation of integral local density of states (ILDOS, top), projected density of states on the molecules (PDOS, middle) and projected density of states for every atom of the molecule (PDOS, bottom).

Figure 12: Charge density difference analysis for most stable full coverage adsorbed configuration of MBTH. Blue and green color correspond to accumulation and deficit of charge density, respectively

490 More details on the molecule-surface binding are provided by the charge
491 density difference analysis. Fig.12 show the charge density difference ($\Delta\rho(r)$),
492 plotted with an isosurface of $\pm 0.001 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$ for the most stable configuration
493 at full coverage of MBTH. For better visualization of the isosurface, we rep-
494 resented only one molecule on the surface in the same adsorption topology
495 as at full coverage.

496 $\Delta\rho(r)$ shows charge density accumulation between the exocyclic sulfur
497 atom and one unsaturated copper. In addition a charge density deficit is
498 observed on the S_{exo} and Cu_{cus} atoms, confirming again the formation of a
499 covalent bond between these atoms. We also observe charge density accu-
500 mulation on one unsaturated oxygen atom and charge density deficit on the
501 hydrogen of the NH group confirming the H-bonding NH...O.

502

503 The Bader charge analysis for MBTH form reveals an electron trans-
504 fer from the organic layer to the oxide. We calculated the values of 0.15
505 e/molecule at full coverage. The electrons were redistributed in the oxide,
506 whereas the electrons distribution after adsorption remains unchanged in
507 the metallic part of the slab substrate. The electrons redistribution on the
508 molecules concerns all atoms. The exocyclic sulfur atoms lose electrons,
509 whereas endocyclic sulfur atoms gain electrons and the nitrogen atom charge
510 remains unchanged before and after adsorption. Analysis for the most stable
511 form of adsorbed thiolate at full coverage also confirms the nature of cova-
512 lent bonding between the S_{exo} and Cu_{cus} atoms and between the N and Cu_{csa}
513 atoms.
514

515 4. Conclusion

516 The interaction of the organic inhibitor 2-mercaptobenzothiole (MBT)
517 under thione (MBTH) and thiolate (MBT°) forms with an oxidized copper
518 surface modeled by a $Cu(111)||Cu_2O(111)$ slab was investigated by DFT.
519 We analyzed the structural and energetic trends to determine the most sta-
520 ble adsorption configuration, and more details about the molecule-surface
521 interaction were provided by the electronic structure analysis.

522 Two thicknesses of the oxide overlayer were considered (5.89 and 11.07
523 Å) and gave similar results. The oxide surface was considered in the dry,
524 hydrated and hydroxylated states at full coverage.

525 At low coverage, the molecules are in tilted adsorption mode. Both forms
526 of MBT bind via S_{exo} atom to Cu_{cus} and two carbon atoms in the aromatic
527 ring are bonded with adjacent Cu_{cus} . In addition MBT° binds via N atoms
528 to Cu_{csa} , instead of $NH...O_{up}$ H-bonding for MBTH.

529 At full coverage, the molecules can form a dense and ordered monolayer
530 by standing perpendicular to the surface. The $S_{exo}-Cu_{cus}$; $NH-O_{up}$ and $S_{exo}-$
531 Cu_{cus} ; $N-Cu_{csa}$ orientations are favored for MBTH and MBT° forms, respec-
532 tively. For both forms, the exocyclic sulfur atom is more reactive and binds
533 covalently to Cu_{cus} . In the thiolate form, the nitrogen is more reactive and
534 binds covalently to Cu_{csa} , whereas in the thione form, a $NH...O_{up}$ H-bond is
535 formed.

536 The adsorption of the molecules leads to recover the high symmetry of
537 the Cu_{cus} sites broken on the bare $Cu_2O(111)$ surface. Thus both forms of
538 the molecule are able to stabilize the surface by bond-making between the

539 S_{exo} and Cu_{cus} atoms. However, for MBT°, bond making between the N
540 and Cu_{csa} atoms leads to the surface reconstruction of Cu_{csa} sites by bond
541 elongation with the adjacent O atoms.

542 The adsorption energy shows strong interaction of MBT with the Cu(111)||Cu₂O(111)
543 surface and a similar trend for the two studied Cu₂O layer thicknesses.

544 The normalization of the adsorption energy to a unit area shows that the
545 full layer formation is favored as compared to the single molecule adsorption.
546 The high adsorption energy is confirmed by the electronic analysis, which
547 evidences the formation of strong bonds between the molecule and the oxi-
548 dized copper surface. Our calculations suggest that the substitution of water
549 or OH groups by MBT molecule is exothermic, the adsorption of MBT is
550 favored whatever the surface state of the oxide film. All these results suggest
551 that MBT strongly adsorbs on copper covered by an ultra thin oxide film and
552 contribute to explain the corrosion protection efficiency of MBT molecule.

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